

SHAROF RASHIDOV IS A UNIQUE CREATOR, STATE FIGURE**Suyarova Aynur Ibodullaevna**

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Abstract: Sharof Rashidov always looked forward to the future. He developed the ability to analyze events and draw conclusions. His experience in journalism and literature helped him make the right decisions. Until the end of his life, he did not turn away from creativity - he read and wrote.

In this article, the life and creative path of the honorable creator of our nation, statesman Sharof Rashidov were given historical outlines.

Keywords: creative, artistic work, journalism, social,

The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 27, 2017 "On the celebration of the 100th anniversary of the birth of the famous statesman and writer Sharif Rashidov" mentions the honoring of Sh. Rashidov's bright memory. Because he made an incomparable contribution to the development of the country, literature and culture with his selfless work, social and creative activities during the Soviet totalitarian regime.

Sh. Rashidov was born in 1917 in the village of Sovungarlik (today Sharof Rashidov) of Jizzakh region in a peasant family.

His father Rashid Khalilov was an ordinary farmer. From dawn to dusk, he worked in the fields for the sake of his children. Father Rashid had 6 sons - Kamal (1915), Sharaf (1917), Sahab (1920), Isom (1923), Asil (1926), Nasir (1930).

Their parents were among the literate people of their time. His mother, Koysinoy, graduated from the girls' school, could read and write in Arabic. Rashid father finished primary education.

In 1926, Sharof Rashidov went to the 7-year school in his native village. After graduating from school in 1933, he entered the local pedagogical technical school. Having graduated from this educational institution with excellent marks, Sharof continued his studies

at the Faculty of Philology of Samarkand State University (Uzbekistan State University) in 1937. While studying at Oliyogoh, he worked at the "Samarkand" publishing house.

Sh.Rashidov did not give up reading and writing books even when he was the head of the state. He believed that in order to meet the demands of the times, he should be knowledgeable and work tirelessly on himself.

In June 1941, graduates of SamSU defended their diploma theses. At the same time, German Nazis invaded the territory of the former union. During this period, the second world war, the most terrible and bloody in the history of mankind, reached its peak.

In August 1941, hundreds of students and teachers of SamSU went to war. Sh.Rashidov joined the Red Army along with them. He was sent to Frunze (now Bishkek), the capital of Kyrgyzstan, for infantry training.

Later, he was awarded the Order of the Red Star for bravery in the battles on the outskirts of Moscow. The document kept in the archives of the Union Ministry of Defense states: "After the company commander was physically destroyed in the late battle for the villages of Pena and Arinino, the junior commander of the company Rashidov assumed the command of the company. He inspired the warriors to perform the task positively by the example of his personal heroism. Moved in the front line of the company and was injured" (excerpt from order No. 306/n of the Commander-in-Chief of the Kalininsky Front on August 28, 1942 awarding Sh. Rashidov with the Order of the Red Star).

Sh.Rashidov returned to Jizzakh after receiving a serious injury and being treated for a long time in Revda, Sverdlovsk (Yekaterinburg) region. Due to the lack of teachers in the school, he acted as a school director and teacher.

In 1943, Sharof Rashidov was appointed editor-in-chief of the newspaper "Lenin Yoli" (now "Zarafshan") of Samarkand region. In 1947, he began to edit the newspaper "Kyzil Uzbekistan", the main publication of the Republic, and was elected a deputy of the Supreme Soviet of Uzbekistan. In 1949, he was appointed chairman of the Union of Writers of Uzbekistan.

In March 1956, Sh.Rashidov came to the Central Committee of the former Union with the demand that in 1937-1938 mature scientists and writers of Uzbekistan were unfairly tried under the label of "enemy of the people" and that they should be acquitted.

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The famous statesman, the creator never sat in his room and gave orders over the phone. He always lived in the development of events, walked among the people and was aware of their joys and problems. He served the people as a farmer in the field, a builder in construction, and a worker in production.

Sharof Rashidov is a well-known artist and statesman. In 1935, he graduated from Jizzakh Pedagogical Technical College and worked as a school teacher. In 1941, he graduated from the Faculty of Philology of Samarkand State University. He participated in the Second World War in 1941-1942. From 1943, he was the editor of the newspaper "Lenin Yoli", 1944 - 1947, the secretary of the Samarkand oblate committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan, 1947 - 1949, the editor of the newspaper "Kyzil Uzbekistan", 1950 - 1959, the chairman of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Uzbek SSR, 1959 - 1983, the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan. worked as the first secretary.

Sharof Rashidov led Uzbekistan for a quarter of a century, which is considered one of the most difficult periods in the history of our republic. In 1959, when he was the first secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan, the era of "warmth" began in the USSR thanks to N.S. Khrushchev, the principle of peaceful coexistence with Western countries was promoted, and a serious effort was made to improve the living conditions of the population inside the country, the Bolsheviks about communism the people's faith in the fairy tale, which had almost

disappeared, began to revive. To further strengthen this faith, one of the most serious documents included the announcement of the construction of communism in 1980.

In March 1959, he was elected the first secretary (head of state) of Uzbekistan.

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